

Investigating the Influence of Process Parameters on Microstructure and Mechanical Performance of Dissimilar Al–Steel Joints Fabricated by Friction Stir Welding

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ABSTRACT

Friction Stir Welding (FSW) has emerged as a promising solid-state joining technique for dissimilar material systems, particularly aluminium–steel combinations, which are otherwise difficult to join using conventional fusion welding. This study investigates the effect of process parameters on the microstructural evolution and mechanical performance of dissimilar joints between AA6061 aluminium alloy and austenitic stainless steel (SS304/SS316). Experimental trials were conducted using a vertical milling machine under varying process conditions, and the resulting joints were evaluated through tensile testing, microstructural characterization, radiographic inspection, hardness measurements, and corrosion testing.

The results reveal that the heat input governed by the rotational-to-traverse speed ratio significantly influences grain refinement, intermetallic formation, and joint integrity. The stir zone exhibited dynamically recrystallized fine grains, while tensile strength decreased with increasing crosshead speed. Radiographic analysis confirmed defect-free joints under optimized conditions, and corrosion resistance remained stable. However, tool degradation and challenges in welding thicker sections were identified as critical limitations. The study contributes to understanding process–structure–property

relationships in dissimilar FSW joints and provides insights for optimizing industrial applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand for lightweight, high-strength hybrid structures has significantly increased in aerospace, automotive, and marine industries. Dissimilar joining of aluminum and steel is particularly attractive due to the combination of low density and high strength. However, conventional fusion welding techniques often lead to the formation of brittle intermetallic compounds (IMCs), residual stresses, and distortion due to large differences in thermal properties.

Friction Stir Welding (FSW), a solid-state joining process, eliminates melting and reduces IMC formation, thereby improving joint performance. Despite its advantages, challenges remain in controlling material flow, optimizing process parameters, and ensuring tool durability, especially in dissimilar systems. [1 – 4].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

R.S. Mishra et al. [1] in his research work, he reported the first results using friction stir processing (FSP) and the feasibility of friction stir processing to produce a microstructure amenable to high strain rate super plasticity in a commercial aluminum alloy, optimum super plasticity was observed in a friction stir processed 7075 Al alloy at 490°C with a strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$.

Patrick B. Berbon et al. [2] in his study on friction stir processed aluminum alloys Al-Ti-Cu and Al-Ti-Ni were investigated and he concluded that the friction stir processing of nanophase aluminum alloys led to high strength of 650 MPa with good ductility above 10%. Improvements in ductility were due to a significantly improved homogenization of the microstructure during FS processing. The FSP technique is amenable to produce ductile, very high specific strength aluminum alloys.

Z.Y. Ma et al. [3] in his investigation on friction stir processing of 7075 Al alloy he concluded that friction stir processing with different processing parameters, resulting in two fine-grained 7075Al alloys with a grain size of 3.8 and 7.5 μm . Heat treatment at 490°C for 1 hour showed that the fine grain microstructures were stable at high temperatures. Superplastic investigations in the temperature range of 420 – 530°C and strain rate range of 1×10^{-3} to $1 \times 10^{-1} s^{-1}$ demonstrated that a decrease in grain size resulted in significantly enhanced super plasticity and a shift to higher optimum strain rate and lower optimum deformation temperature. For the 3.8 μm 7075Al alloy, superplastic elongations of >1250% were obtained at 480°C in the strain rate range of 3×10^{-3} to $3 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$ whereas the 7.5 μm 7075Al alloy exhibited a maximum ductility of 1042% at 500°C and $3 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$. The analyses of the superplastic data for the two alloys revealed a stress exponent of 2, an inverse grain size dependence of 2, and an activation energy close to that for grain boundary self-diffusion. This indicates that grain boundary sliding is the main deformation mechanism for the FSP 7075Al.

R.S. Mishra et al. [4] in his work on fabrication of surface composite by friction stir processing technique, he concluded that Al-SiC surface composites with different volume fractions of particles were successfully fabricated. The thickness of the surface composite layer ranged from 50 to 200 μm . The SiC particles were uniformly distributed in the aluminum matrix. The surface composites have excellent bonding with the aluminum alloy substrate. The microhardness of the surface composite reinforced with 27vol.%SiC of 0.7 μm average particle size was 173 HV, almost double of the 5083Al alloy substrate (85 HV). The solid-state processing and very fine microstructure that results are also desirable for high performance surface composites.

S.R. Sharma et al. [5] in his investigation on fatigue behavior of friction stir processed A356 alloy, he concluded that FSP resulted in a significant breakup and uniform distribution of Si particles in the aluminum matrix as well as elimination of porosity. This leads to an improvement in fatigue stress threshold stress $>80\%$ in the stir zone of the FSP sample. This improvement in fatigue properties is attributed to an increased effective crack length and reduction in crack growth rate. FSP can be used as a tool to locally modify the microstructures in regions experiencing high fatigue loading and thus significantly improve the overall performance of aluminum casting.

3. EXPERIMENTAL Details

3.1 Experimental plan:

It describes a sequence of steps for preparing the samples, experimentation plan and testing, as shown below in the flow chart

Process Optimization
by Taguchi method

Adding Filler Material

Tool Design and
Fabrication

↓
Friction Stir Processing

↓
Testing and Results

↓
Conclusion

↓

3.2 Material Selection:

Here we are selecting Aluminum from the 6xxx series alloys. When considered for fabrication, these alloys are selected mainly for superior corrosion resistance such as in specialized chemical tanks and piping or for their excellent electric conductivity as in bus bar applications. These alloys are welded with matching filler material. Aluminum 6061 is selected from the 6xxx series Alloys.

3.3 Stainless steel

Stainless steel is a group of iron-based alloys that contain a minimum of approximately 11% chromium, a composition that prevents the iron from rusting and also provides heat-resistant properties. Different types of stainless steel include the elements carbon (from 0.03% to greater than 1.00%), nitrogen, aluminium, silicon, sulfur, titanium, nickel, copper, selenium, niobium, and molybdenum. Specific types of stainless steel are often designated by a three-digit number, e.g., *304 stainless*.

Stainless steel's resistance to ferric formation results from the presence of chromium in the alloy, which forms a passive film that protects the underlying material from corrosion attack, and can self-heal in the presence of oxygen. Corrosion resistance can be increased further, by:

- increasing the chromium content to levels above 11%;
- addition of 8% or higher amounts of nickel and
- addition of molybdenum (which also improves resistance to "pitting corrosion").

The addition of nitrogen also improves resistance to pitting corrosion and increases mechanical strength. Thus, there are numerous grades of stainless steel with varying chromium and molybdenum contents to suit the environment the alloy must endure.

Resistance to corrosion and staining, low maintenance, and familiar luster make stainless steel an ideal material for many applications where both the strength of steel and corrosion resistance are required. Moreover, stainless steel can be rolled into sheets, plates, bars, wire, and tubing. These can be used in cookware, cutlery, surgical instruments, major appliances, construction material in large buildings, industrial equipment (e.g., in paper mills, chemical plants, water treatment), and storage tanks and tankers for chemicals and food products. The material's corrosion resistance, the ease with which it can be steam-cleaned and sterilized, and the absence of the need for surface coatings have prompted the use of stainless steel in kitchens and food processing plants.

3.3.1 Stainless Steel families

There are five main families, which are primarily classified by their crystalline structure: austenitic, ferritic, martensitic, duplex, and precipitation hardening.

Austenitic stainless steel

Austenitic stainless steel is the largest family of stainless steels, making up about two-thirds of all stainless steel production (see production figures below). They possess an austenitic microstructure, which is a face-centered cubic crystal structure. This microstructure is achieved by alloying steel with sufficient nickel and/or manganese and nitrogen to maintain an austenitic microstructure at all temperatures, ranging from the cryogenic region to the melting point. Thus, austenitic stainless steels are not hardenable by heat treatment since they possess the same microstructure at all temperatures. Austenitic stainless steels can be further subdivided into two sub-groups, 200 series and 300 series:

- 300 series are chromium-nickel alloys that achieve their austenitic microstructure almost exclusively by nickel alloying; some very highly-alloyed grades include some nitrogen to reduce nickel requirements. 300 series is the largest group and the most widely used.

- Type 304: The best-known grade is Type 304, also known as 18/8 and 18/10 for its composition of 18% chromium and 8%/10% nickel, respectively.¹
- Type 316: The second most common austenitic stainless steel is Type 316. The addition of 2% molybdenum provides greater resistance to acids and localized corrosion caused by chloride ions. Low-carbon versions, such as 316L or 304L, have carbon contents below 0.03% and are used to avoid corrosion problems caused by welding.

Experimental

A semi automation milling machine was used for friction stir processing (FSW) of aluminum alloy. The machine was a maximum speed 6000 rpm and 10-horse power. Test piece was clamped in the fixture tightly. Initially the rotating pin was inserted into a predrilled hole, which will facilitate the startup of welding. Tool tilt angle was 2degree processing began at spindle speed of 900 rpm and travel rate of 25mm/min. since tool plunge was to the extent of 3mm and plate thickness the same step was repeated for tool. The result was two side welded plates. The plates where then subjected to mechanical testing. In the present work the influence of speed, feed on the performance of FSW such as tensile strength is evaluated at different experimental conditions

Figure 13: Vertical Milling Machine

Figure 14: Different Speeds in rpm

As received Al6061 & SS316 sheets are used for FSW. The process of FSW begins with the work piece being firmly clamped to a worktable via backing plate which is placed on the Dynamometer. A small hole is drilled at the beginning of the sheet to initiate the penetration of the tool. The rotating pin is forced into the work piece and moved along the desired direction with a specific combination of rotational and translation speeds. Frictional heating is produced from the relative motion of the rotating shoulder with respect to the sheet being processed, while the rotating pin deforms rather generates a ‘stirring’ action which locally heats up and creates severe plastic deformation in the material. FSW can be considered as a hot working process in which a large amount of deformation is imparted to the work piece than the rotating pin and the shoulder. The FSW tool and experimental set up. FSW processed zone is characterized by dynamic recrystallization which arises through either localized or large scale instabilities forming narrow or extended adiabatic shear bands. There is an apparent extrusion like behavior of material around the pin tool, the process is more characteristic of solid state flow facilitated by the adiabatic shear creating recrystallization regimes to accommodate the large deformations at high deformation rates. The result of this process is a homogeneous, equiaxed, dynamically recrystallized, fine grained material. In order to process the complete sheet, overlapping passes are used. The process is initiated by drilling a hole in the work piece, as it allows the pin to easily penetrate into the work piece as there is not enough heat generate at the beginning of the process to make the material soft. The forces generated during the entire process are recorded using the data acquisition system. The processed sheets are then prepared for microstructural and mechanical testing.

5.1 Experimental Process

5.1.1 Material Used for 3 mm Thickness Plates

- Aluminium 6061
- Stainless-steel 304

5.1.2 Specification of Work Pieces

The aluminum work piece of the dimensions

- Length of plate: 125 mm
- Thickness of plate: 3mm
- Width of plate: 85 mm
- Total no of plates: 1
- No of joints: 1

The stainless-steel work piece of the dimensions

- Length of plate: 125 mm
- Thickness of plate: 3mm
- Width of plate: 85 mm
- Total no of plates: 1
- No of joints: 1

Specification of Work Pieces

Material Used for 5 mm Thickness Plates

- Aluminium 6061
- Stainless-steel 304

5.1.3 Specification of Machine

The friction stir welding machine specification

- Model: HMT FN2-EV
- Control: Automatic and Manual
- Spindle Motor Power: 10 HP

- Spindle Speed: 35-1800 rpm
- Cutting feed: 1-4000 mm/min
- Working surface area: 255x196x197mm
- Longitudinal Travel(X): 1000 mm
- Cross Travel(Y): 400mm
- Head Stock travel: 620 mm

5.1.4 Friction Stir Welding Machine

Figure 16: Friction stir welding machine

AL-6061

SS-304

Figure 17: Specimens of Different Alloys

AL-6061 & SS-304

Specimens before FSW process

Figure 18: Specimens before FSW process

Table 1 Main process parameters in friction stir welding.

Parameters	Effects
Rotational speed	Frictional heat,-stirring, oxide layer breaking and mixing of material
Tilting angle	The appearance of the weld, thinning
Welding speed	Appearance , heat control
Down force	Frictional heat , maintaining contact conditions

Fixture Setup of Friction Stir Welding Process:

Figure 19: Fixture Setup

Figure 20: Taper (conical)

Material: H-13 Tool Steel (C-0.4%, Mn-0.4%, Si-1.00%, Cr-5.25%, Mo-1.35%, V-1.0)

Tools Used for Friction Stir Welding Process:

2 D Drawings of Tool Used for Friction Stir Welding Process:

Figure 21: CONICAL

Experimental Work on Friction Stir Welding Machine

Figure 22: Experimental Work on Friction Stir Welding Machine

Figure 23: Specimens after FSW Process

Specimens after Tensile Test is Performed on Universal Testing Machines

5.1.5 Material Used for 5 mm Thickness Plates

- Aluminium 6061
- Stainless-steel 316

5.1.6 Specification of Work Pieces

The aluminum work piece of the dimensions

- Length of plate: 125 mm
- Thickness of plate: 3mm
- Width of plate: 85 mm
- Total no of plates: 1
- No of joints: 1

The stainless-steel work piece of the dimensions

- Length of plate: 125 mm
- Thickness of plate: 3mm
- Width of plate: 85 mm
- Total no of plates: 1
- No of joints: 1

Figure 24: Aluminium plate

Figure 25: Stainless Steel plate

Experimental Work on Friction Stir Welding Machine

Figure 26: Welding plate

While welding 5mm thickness plate tool pin is broken in the middle of the welding .so selecting material is important

5.2 Types of Tests

The following tests are to be performed on the specimens after friction stir welding (FSW) of alloys

5.2.1 Universal Testing Machine

A universal testing machine (UTM), also known as a universal tester, materials testing machine or materials test frame, is used to test the tensile strength and compressive strength of materials. The specimen is placed in the machine between the grips and an extensometer if required can automatically record the change in gauge length during the test. If an extensometer is not fitted, the machine itself can record the displacement between its cross heads on which the specimen is held. However, this method not only records the change in length of the specimen but also all other extending / elastic components of the testing machine and its drive systems including any slipping of the specimen in the grips.

Figure 27: Universal Testing Machine

5.2.3 Vickers Hardness Test

Hardness is a characteristic of a material, not a fundamental physical property. It is defined as the resistance to indentation, and it is determined by measuring the permanent depth of the indentation. More simply put, when using a fixed force (load) and a given indenter, the smaller the indentation, the harder the material. Indentation hardness value is obtained by measuring the depth or the area of the indentation using one of over 12 different test methods.

The Vickers hardness test method, also referred to as a micro hardness test method, is mostly used for small parts, thin sections, or case depth work. The Vickers method is based on an optical measurement system. The Micro hardness test procedure, ASTM E-384, specifies a range of light loads using a diamond indenter to make an indentation which is measured and converted to a hardness value. It is very useful for testing on a wide type of materials, but test samples must be highly polished to enable measuring the size of the impressions. A square base pyramid shaped diamond is used for testing in the Vickers scale. Typically loads are very light, ranging from 10gm to 1kgf, although "Macro" Vickers loads can range up to 30 kg or more. The Micro hardness methods are used to test on metals, ceramics, and composites - almost any type of material. Since the test indentation is very small in a Vickers test, it is useful for a variety of applications: testing very thin materials like foils or measuring the surface of a part, small parts or small areas, measuring individual microstructures, or measuring the depth of case hardening by sectioning a part and making a series of indentations to describe a profile of the change in hardness.

Figure 29: Vickers hardness test machine

5.2.4 Corrosion Test (Salt spray test)

The salt spray test is standard and popular corrosion test method. it is used to check corrosion resistance of the materials and surface coating. the materials to be tested are metallic and finished with surface coating which is intended to provide a degree of corrosion protection to the underlying metals.

The apparatus for testing consists of a closed testing chamber, where a salt water solution is atomized by means of spray nozzle using pressurized air. This produces a corrosive environment of dense salt water fog in the chamber so that test sample exposed to the environment. chamber volume varies from supplier to supplier it depends on size of the materials.

6. Results

- Tensile test
- Micro structure
- Radiographic test
- Vickers hardness test
- Corrosion test

Tensile Results

Cross Head speed (mm/min)	Tensile Yield Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)
0.5	276	497
1	270	470
2	265	425

With an increase in the CHS, a reduction in the tensile properties of the weld is observed.

Specimens after Tensile Test is Performed on Universal Testing Machines

Figure34: Before Tensile test

Figure35: After Tensile test

Figure36: Tensile sample

Cross head travel 2mm/min

Figure 37: Displacement Vs Load

Cross head travel 1mm/min

Figure 38: Displacement Vs Load

Cross head travel 0.5mm/min

Figure 39: Displacemnt Vs Load

Micro structure

Figure 40: Microstructure of HAZ-Aluminium

Figure 41: Microstructure of HAZ-stainless-steel

Figure 42: Microstructure of TMAZ-Aluminium

Figure 43: Microstructure of TMAZ-Stainless-steel

Figure 44: Microstructure of SZ (stir zone)

Specimen orientation: Cross Section

Etchant : Oxalic acid+2%HF

Magnification : 100X

Observation : Thermomechanically affected zone (TMAZ)-Stainless-steel(SS) zone shows elongated austenite grains aligned in the direction of stirring.

Heat affected zone(HAZ)-SS Microstructure of the HAZ-SS zone shows fine austenite grains in the matrix of austenite.

TMAZ-AL(Aluminium)-Microstructure of the TMAZ-AL zone shows elongated grains and intermetallic particles aligned in the direction of stirring.

HAZ-AL-Microstructure of the HAZ-AL zone shows the fine grains and intermetallic particles randomly distributed in the matrix of the aluminium solid solution.

Stire zone (SZ)-Microstructure of the weld zone shows mixture of austenitic grains and intermetallic particles of aluminium aligned in the direction of stirring. Some coarse particles and porosity observed in the weld zone.

Vickers Hardness Test

Table 26: Hardness Test for Aluminium

Trial	Specimen	Load applied(kgf)	Vickers Hardness Value
1	Aluminium	5	104
2	Aluminium	5	102
3	Aluminium	5	108

Table 27: Hardness Test for Stainless-Steel

Trial	Specimen	Load applied(kgf)	Vickers Hardness Value
1	Stainless-Steel	5	204
2	Stainless-Steel	5	210
3	Stainless-Steel	5	206

Corrosion Test [Salt Spray test]

Figure 46: Before Corrosion

Figure 47: After Corrosion

Test temperature(C) -35.1

Volume of solution collected (ml)-1.2

Specified test duration(hour) – 1

Observation Interval -15 minutes

Specimen cleaning –water/blow dry

Observations:

Time (minutes)	Observations
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0	No corrosion products observed
15	No corrosion products observed
30	No corrosion products observed
45	No corrosion products observed
60	No corrosion products observed

After 1 hour of salt spray Exposure, no corrosion products observed on sample surface.

Conclusions:

- The long service life of FSW tool with minimum wear is critical during Al/steel Welding.
- One of the critical challenges to bring Al/steel dissimilar joints to practical application is reliability and durability.
- To increase the material mixing between dissimilar aluminium alloys and steels and improve the joint mechanical performance, hybrid dissimilar welding by incorporating additional heat source, such as laser and arc, to soften the hard material was developed.
- An increasing number of applications will be found for FSW in the fabrication of Al/steel composite structure with high quality.
- Although a number of challenges still exist, FSW offers very attractive possibilities for commercial success.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. F. Lancaster, *The Physics of Welding*, 2nd ed. Oxford, U.K.: Pergamon Press, 1986.
- [2] S. Kou, *Welding Metallurgy*, 2nd ed. New York, NY, USA: Wiley-Interscience, 2003.
- [3] R. W. Messler, *Principles of Welding: Processes, Physics, Chemistry, and Metallurgy*. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 1999.
- [4] ASM International, *ASM Handbook, Volume 6: Welding, Brazing, and Soldering*. Materials Park, OH, USA: ASM International, 1993.
- [5] T. J. Lienert *et al.*, “Welding and joining of dissimilar metals,” *Welding Journal*, vol. 85, no. 6, pp. 1s–8s, 2006.
- [6] E. Taban *et al.*, “Dissimilar welding of Aluminium and steel: Challenges and solutions,” *Materials & Design*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 2305–2311, 2010.
- [7] R. S. Mishra and Z. Y. Ma, “Friction stir welding and processing,” *Materials Science and Engineering: R: Reports*, vol. 50, no. 1–2, pp. 1–78, 2005.
- [8] P. L. Threadgill *et al.*, “Friction stir welding of aluminium alloys,” *International Materials Reviews*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 49–93, 2009.
- [9] T. Watanabe *et al.*, “Joining of Aluminium alloy to steel by friction stir welding,” *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 178, no. 1–3, pp. 342–349, 2006.
- [10] S. Katayama, *Handbook of Laser Welding Technologies*. Cambridge, U.K.: Woodhead Publishing, 2013.
- [11] Z. Sun and J. C. Ion, “Laser welding of Aluminium alloys,” *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 101, no. 1–3, pp. 1–8, 2000.
- [12] Y. Chen, K. Nakata, and M. Ushio, “Effect of tool offset on friction stir welding of aluminium and steel,” *Materials Science and Engineering A*, vol. 420, no. 1–2, pp. 174–181, 2006.

- [13] H. Liu, H. Fujii, M. Maeda, and K. Nogi, "Influence of process parameters on friction stir welding of dissimilar aluminium alloys," *Materials Letters*, vol. 57, no. 25–26, pp. 4104–4110, 2003.
- [14] F. Sierra, J. C. Viala, and J. F. Deschaux-Beaume, "Dissimilar welding of aluminium to steel by laser process," *Materials & Design*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 1099–1108, 2010.
- [15] J. Yan, Z. Xu, Z. Li, L. Li, and S. Yang, "Microstructure and mechanical properties of laser welded aluminium–steel joints," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 210, no. 12, pp. 1623–1631, 2010.
- [16] A. Kouadri-David, "Laser welding of aluminium to steel," *Materials Science and Engineering A*, vol. 363, no. 1–2, pp. 1–10, 2003.
- [17] M. J. Torkamany, J. Sabbaghzadeh, and S. Poursalehi, "Effect of laser parameters on dissimilar welding of aluminium to steel," *Optics & Laser Technology*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 420–425, 2010.
- [18] A. Meco, S. Ganguly, and T. J. B. M. de Hosson, "Effect of heat input on intermetallic compound formation in laser welding of dissimilar metals," *Materials & Design*, vol. 64, pp. 551–560, 2014.
- [19] J. Fan, H. Thomy, and F. Vollertsen, "Conduction mode laser welding of dissimilar aluminium–steel joints," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 221, pp. 95–101, 2015.
- [20] P. Peyre, R. Fabbro, and P. Merrien, "Reactive wetting and bonding mechanisms in laser welding of aluminum to steel," *Materials Science and Engineering A*, vol. 444, no. 1–2, pp. 327–338, 2007.
- [21] F. Sierra, J. C. Viala, and J. F. Deschaux-Beaume, "Laser welding of aluminium to steel using filler materials," *Welding Journal*, vol. 87, no. 5, pp. 135s–142s, 2008.
- [22] X. Cao and M. Jahazi, "Effect of welding speed on aluminum alloy weld quality," *Materials & Design*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 2033–2042, 2009.

- [23] Z. Sun and J. C. Ion, “Laser welding of aluminium alloys,” *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 101, no. 1–3, pp. 1–8, 2000.
- [24] W. M. Steen and J. Mazumder, *Laser Material Processing*, 4th ed., London, UK: Springer, 2010.
- [25] A. Gullino, M. Matteis, and M. D’Aiuto, “A review of aluminium-to-steel welding technologies for automotive applications,” *Metals*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 315–332, 2019.